

GENETIC DIVERSITY STUDIES IN DESI COTTON [*Gossypium arboreum* (L.)]D. B. Pawar^{*1}, Rathod A. H., D. K. Zate and Borgaonkar S. B.^{2,3,4}^{*1}M.Sc. students, Department of Genetics and Plant Breeding, College of Agriculture, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.² Assistant Breeder, Breeder Seed Production Unit, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.³ Assistant Professor, Department of Agriculture Botany, College of Agriculture, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.⁴ Cotton Breeder, Cotton Research Station, MB Farm, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani, Maharashtra, India.

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MS Received: 10.11.2024; MS Revised:21.12.2024; MS Accepted:22.12.2024)

MS 3320

(RESEARCH PAPER IN GENETICS AND PLANT BREEDING)

Abstract

Thirty-two accessions of desi cotton were used to study the nature and magnitude of genetic divergence using Mahalanobis's D^2 Statistics. The data for twelve important quantitative traits recorded from the genotypes raised in randomized block design with two replications during kharif 2023-24 at Cotton Research Station, Mahboob Baugh Farm, Vasantrya Naik Marathwada Krishi Vidyapeeth, Parbhani. On the base of D^2 values. Thirty-two accessions of desi cotton were evaluated to determine the extent of variation for different morphological characters. These accessions were categorized into four clusters. Mahalanobis D^2 statistic revealed considerable genetic diversity within and among the four clusters. Percent contribution of twelve different characters toward genetic divergence is presented in table number 2. Among the twelve characters studied, the maximum contribution towards genetic divergence was contributed by plant height (43.35 %) followed by fiber fineness (17.54 %), upper half mean length (10.48 %), uniformity ratio (5.65 %), fiber strength (5.44 %) and seed cotton yield per plant (3.23 %). Cluster IV had the greatest cluster mean for five characters, including plant height, number of sympodia, number of bolls per plant, boll weight, ginning percentage and seed cotton yield per plant, according to the overall assessment of cluster means for all characters. The cluster mean is presented in table number 3. Cluster I had the highest cluster mean for four parameters, including, uniformity ratio, fibre strength, upper half mean length and seed cotton yield per plant while cluster III was indicated highest cluster mean for a single character, days to 50 % flowering. The highest cluster mean was recorded for uniformity ratio in Cluster I and for seed cotton yield per plant in Cluster IV.

Key words: Cluster, genetic diversity, desi cotton, D^2 statistics

Introduction

Cotton (*Gossypium hirsutum* L.) is an important economical crop grown for fibre in more than 70 countries of the world, besides this it is also an important source of edible oil, protein and cottonseed meal for animals. Cotton belongs to Malvaceae family and genus *Gossypium*, which consists of five allotetraploid and forty-five diploid species among them only four species are cultivated worldwide comprising of two diploids and two tetraploids also called old world and new world species. India has the distinction of growing all the four spinnable lint bearing species of *Gossypium* viz., *G. hirsutum*, *G. barbadense*, *G. arboreum* and *G. herbaceum*. Among these four cultivated species, upland cotton (*G. hirsutum* L.) is known for its production potential, as demonstrated by the release of number of stable varieties and hybrids. Cotton seed had gained the additional economic importance as a major contributor to edible oil, protein and other by-products (Hasan & Latha, 2017). Breeding programmes are determined in the initial step by the variability existing in the base populations. Later, the success of the selected material depends upon the stability of the characters under selection. Thus, understanding the genetic makeup of the crop and the architecture of character set up in that crop are basic to a plant breeder. It is necessary to estimate the amount of variability present in a population in order to exploit it for trait improvement, which is required for genetic improvement in any crop species. Genetic distance estimations are used in hybrid crop breeding to select parental combinations with appropriate genetic diversity and to classify germplasm into distinct heterotic groups (Chakraborty et al., 2021). Cotton breeders' ultimate goal is to develop varieties and hybrids with desirable fibre traits and high seed cotton yield. It is necessary to measure the genetic diversity among the genotypes in order to select elite parents for the hybridization programme, as genetic diversity plays an important role in generating heterosis in hybrids between genotypes. Mahalanobis' D^2 statistics is an effective tool for determining the degree of genetic divergence at the genotypic level, as well as a measure of the relationship between geographic distribution and genetic diversity based on generalised distance (Mahalanobis, 1928). Multivariate analysis, utilizing Mahalanobis' D^2 statistics has been found to be a potent biometrical tool in quantifying the degree of divergence in germplasm collection of various crop plants (Rao, 1952). Without making crosses before starting the hybridization programme, the D^2 statistic can be used to select parent combinations (Bhatt, 1970). The observed inter-cluster

distances were greater than intra-cluster distances, suggesting that crossing of genotypes from different clusters could produce favourable transgressive segregants in segregating generations (Nidagundi et al., 2023).

Material And Method

Thirty-two accessions of *desi* cotton were used for characterization, genetic diversity studies in randomized block design with two replications during kharif 2023-2024. The plot size of 0.9×4.5 m² along with spacing of 45 cm \times 22.5 cm was kept to grow the experiment. Recommended package of practices were followed as suitable for the climate conditions of Parbhani. Data were recorded on five randomly tagged plants for viz., days to 50 per cent flowering, number of monopodia, number of sympodia, plant height, number of bolls per plant, boll weight, ginning percentage, uniformity ratio, fiber strength, upper half mean length, micronaire, and seed cotton yield per plant. Statistical analysis: Mahalanobis (1936) defined the distance between two populations as D^2 , which was obtained by Tocher's method, described by Rao (1952). Grouping of variety into various clusters was done and average intra and inter cluster distance were estimated.

Result And Discussion

The basic step in successful breeding programme is the identification of diverse parental lines which might also possess precious gene combinations. D^2 statistics is one such 70 effective tool which helps in the choice of genetically diverse parents for exploitation of hybrid vigour in hybridization programmes. The D^2 statistics is mainly aimed at identifying the degree of diversification and contribution of individual trait towards the total genetic divergence. The D^2 approach operates at each inter-cluster level and intra-cluster level thereby offers a dependable measure of genetic diversity present amongst a large number of genotypes at a time. In the present study, 32 genotypes have been subjected for D^2 analysis and they have been grouped into 4 diverse clusters following Tocher's method.

Based on the D^2 results, thirty-two accessions were categorized in to four clusters. The genotypes categorised in different clusters are presented in table number 1. The clusters are presented in the form of Tocher diagram. Cluster I have reported the maximum (28) number of genotypes followed by genotypes, Cluster III (02) genotypes. Only one genotype was found in the remaining clusters II and IV, respectively. Solitary clusters may arise as a result of absolute isolation of extensive gene flow or natural/human selection for rigorous varied adaptive

complexes. These genotypes could be one-of-a-kind and important in breeding programme. Cluster I includes 28 genotypes, viz; DAS 1202, GAM 223, CAN 2030, PBD 22, KWA 1301, GAM 259, MDL 2663, HD 550, CAN 1036, NDLA 266, NDLA 3115, FDK 286, RG 784, DWDA 1702, CAN 1016, GAM 236, CAN 1038, CAN 1032, GAM 255, DAS 752, NDLA 3116, RG 776, PBD 35, JLA 1261, CISA 405, NDLA 2601, PA 740 and PA 810. Whereas, Cluster II includes 01 genotype GAM 360, while Cluster III includes 02 genotypes DWDA 1301, FDK 2811 followed by Cluster IV which includes 01 genotype only NDLA 3133.

Similar findings were reported by Saravanan *et al.*, (2021) in desi cotton grouped 36 genotypes into nine clusters, Chapara *et al.*, (2020) in American cotton grouped 50 genotypes into eight clusters. Valu *et al.*, (2021) grouped 68 genotypes into ten clusters. Sagar *et al.*, (2023) grouped 60 genotypes into eight clusters in desi cotton.

Intra cluster D^2 values ranged from 0.00 to 9.73. The maximum intra cluster D^2 value was observed (9.73) for cluster I followed by cluster III had 8.74. While intra clusters D^2 value was zero for cluster II and cluster IV. The intra and inter cluster distance are presented in table number 5. The intra cluster indicates the diversity among the genotypes grouped in that clusters. Genotypes grouped into same clusters presumably differ little from one another as the aggregate of character is measured. During the study it was also revealed that, the inter cluster values varies from 12.53 to 27.91. The maximum inter cluster distance ($D=27.91$) was observed between cluster IV and cluster III. The minimum inter cluster distance ($D=12.53$) was noticed between cluster II and cluster I.

The highest statistical distance was found between cluster IV and cluster I for yield contributing and fibre traits. The maximum inter cluster distance suggests that the genotypes belonging to these clusters were genetically most divergent, if chosen for further breeding programme, they are likely to give good genotypes with better performances. Similarly, Sagar *et al.*, (2023) observed inter cluster distances were higher than the intra cluster distances showing the presence of wider genetic diversity among the clusters in desi cotton.

Cluster mean for days to 50 % flowering ranged from 63.50 days (cluster IV) to 66.75 days (cluster III). Cluster IV (63.50 days) exhibited early days to 50 percent flowering followed by cluster II (64.50 days). Late flowering was recorded by cluster III (66.75 days) followed by cluster I (65.96 days). Cluster mean for number of monopodia per plant ranged from 6.40 (cluster IV) to 8.95 (cluster II). Highest number of monopodia per plant was recorded for cluster II (8.95) followed by cluster I (7.15) whereas lowest number of monopodia per plant exhibited by cluster IV (6.40) followed by cluster III (7.10). Cluster mean for plant height ranged from 43.56 cm (cluster III) to 98.45 cm (cluster IV). Highest plant height was recorded for cluster IV (98.45 cm) followed by cluster I (85.63 cm) whereas lowest plant height exhibited by cluster III (43.56 cm) followed by cluster II (64.25 cm).

Cluster mean for number of sympodia per plant ranged from 9.50 (cluster III) to 13.35 (cluster II). Highest number of sympodia per plant was recorded for cluster II (13.35) followed by cluster IV (11.20) whereas lowest number of sympodia per plant exhibited by cluster III

Table 1: Grouping of thirty-two cotton genotypes into different clusters

Cluster	Genotypes
Cluster -I	RG 784, NDLA 266, NDLA 3115, CAN 1016, NDLA 3116, GAM 236, CAN 1038, GAM 223, DWDA 1702
Cluster-II	GAM 360
Cluster-III	DWDA 1301, FDK 2811
Cluster-IV	NDLA 3133

Thus, if the crosses were attempted from widely separate clusters, they would throw desired recombinants giving enormous seed cotton yield.

Table 2: Percent contribution of twelve different characters toward genetic divergence in cotton

Sr. No.	Characters	Number of times appearing I th ranking	% Contribution
1	Plant height (cm)	215	43.35
2	Fibre fineness ($\mu\text{g}/\text{inch}$)	87	17.54
3	Upper half mean length (mm)	52	10.48
4	Uniformity ratio (%)	28	5.65
5	Fibre strength (g/tex)	27	5.44
6	Ginning percentage (%)	25	5.04

(9.50) followed by cluster I (9.55). Cluster mean for number of bolls per plant ranged from 13.48 (cluster III) to 22.65 (cluster IV). Highest cluster mean for number of bolls per plant was recorded for cluster IV (22.65) followed by cluster II (20.05) whereas lowest cluster mean for number of bolls per plant was recorded by cluster III (13.48) followed by cluster I (15.41). Boll weight cluster mean was ranged from 2.54 g (cluster III) to 3.38 g (cluster IV). Highest cluster mean for boll weight was recorded for cluster IV (3.38 g) followed by cluster I (3.37 g) whereas lowest boll weight cluster mean was recorded for cluster III (2.54 g) followed by cluster II (2.56 g). Cluster mean for seed cotton yield per plant was ranged from 23.93 g (cluster III) to 55.10 g (Cluster IV). Highest cluster mean for seed cotton yield per plant was recorded for cluster IV (55.10 g) followed cluster I (33.74 g) whereas lowest cluster mean for seed cotton yield per plant was recorded by cluster III (23.93 g) followed by cluster II (26.95).

Cluster mean for ginning percent ranged from 34.87 % (cluster IV) to 37.79 % (cluster II). Highest number of ginning percent was recorded for cluster II (37.79 %) followed by cluster III (35.30 %) whereas lowest cluster mean was recorded by cluster I (34.87 %) and cluster IV (34.87 %). Cluster mean for upper half mean length ranged from 20.15 mm (cluster IV) to 27.11 mm (cluster I). Highest cluster mean for upper half mean length was recorded for cluster I (27.11 mm) followed by cluster III (26.15 mm) whereas lowest cluster mean of upper half mean length was observed by cluster IV (20.15 mm) followed by cluster II (25.56 mm). Cluster mean for fibre strength ranged from 20.80 g tex^{-1} (cluster IV) to 26.90 g tex^{-1} (cluster I). Highest cluster mean for fibre strength was recorded for cluster I (26.90 g tex^{-1}) followed by cluster III (25.10 g tex^{-1}) whereas lowest cluster mean for fibre strength was recorded by cluster IV (20.80 g tex^{-1}) followed by cluster II (24.75 g tex^{-1}).

Cluster mean for fibre fineness ranged from 5.70 $\mu\text{g}/\text{in}$ (cluster I) to 6.65 $\mu\text{g}/\text{in}$ (cluster II). Highest cluster mean for fibre strength was recorded for cluster II (6.65 $\mu\text{g}/\text{in}$) followed by cluster IV (6.20 $\mu\text{g}/\text{in}$) whereas lowest cluster mean for fibre fineness was recorded by cluster I (5.70 $\mu\text{g}/\text{in}$) followed by cluster III (5.75 $\mu\text{g}/\text{in}$). Cluster mean for uniformity ratio ranged from 78.10 % (cluster IV) to 81.65 (cluster I) %. Highest cluster mean for uniformity ratio was observed for cluster I (81.65 %) followed by cluster III (81.05 %) whereas lowest cluster mean for uniformity ratio was observed by cluster IV (78.10 %) followed by cluster IV.

Cluster IV had the greatest cluster mean for five characters, including plant height, number of sympodia, number of bolls per plant, boll weight, ginning percentage and seed cotton yield per plant, according to the overall assessment of cluster means for all characters. The character improvement on the basis of source cluster is given in table number 4. Cluster I had the highest cluster mean for four parameters, including, uniformity ratio, fibre strength, upper half mean length and seed cotton yield per plant while cluster III was indicated highest cluster mean for a single character, days to 50 % flowering. The highest cluster mean for uniformity ratio was recorded in Cluster I whereas, for seed cotton yield per plant in Cluster IV.

On the basis of mean performance, the desired genotypes suggested for tentative breeding programme are as follows:

7	No. of bolls	22	4.44
8	Boll weight (gm)	19	3.83
9	Seed cotton yield per plant (g)	16	3.23
10	Days to 50% flowering	5	1.01

Table 3: Clusters mean for twelve different morphological, yield contributing fibre characters in cotton

Sr. No.	Characters	I	II	III	IV
1	Days to 50% flowering	65.96	64.50	66.75	63.50
2	No. of monopodia	7.15	8.95	7.10	6.40
3	No. of sympodia/plant	9.55	13.35	9.50	11.20
4	Plant height (cm)	85.63	64.25	43.56	98.45
5	No. of bolls/plant	15.41	20.05	13.48	22.65
6	Boll weight (g)	3.37	2.56	2.54	3.38
7	Ginning percentage (%)	34.87	37.79	35.30	34.87
8	Uniformity ratio	81.65	80.50	81.05	78.10
9	Fibre strength (g tex ⁻¹)	26.90	24.75	25.10	20.80
10	Upper half mean length (mm)	27.11	25.56	26.15	20.15
11	Fibre fineness (µg/in)	5.70	6.65	5.75	6.20
12	Seed cotton yield per plant (g)	33.74	26.95	23.93	55.10

Table 4: Characters improvement on the basis of source clusters

Sr. No	Characters	Sources of clusters
1	Days to 50% flowering	III, I
2	No. of monopodia	II, I
3	No. of sympodia/plant	II, IV
4	Plant height (cm)	IV, I
5	No. of bolls/plant	IV, II
6	Boll weight (gm)	IV, I
7	Ginning percentage (%)	II, III
8	Uniformity ratio	I, III
9	Fibre strength (g tex ⁻¹)	I, III
10	Upper half mean length (mm)	I, III
11	Fibre fineness (µg/in)	II, IV
12	Seed cotton yield per plant (g)	IV, I

Table 5: Intra (diagonal) and inter (above diagonal) cluster distance (D²) value for twelve characters in cotton

Clusters	I	II	III	IV
I	9.73	14.23	17.23	18.15
II	14.23	0.00	12.53	22.15
III	17.23	12.53	8.74	27.91
IV	18.15	22.15	27.91	0.00

Fig 1: Cluster formation of thirty-two genotypes by tocher's method in cotton.

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